

The nature and types of extracurricular work in mathematics

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Annotatsiya: Boshlang'ich sinflarda matematikadan sinfdan tashqari o'quv mashg'ulotlarini tashkil qilish va uni o'tkazish bo'yicha bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni mustahkamlash.

Kalit so'zlar: Darsdan tashqari ishlar, matematik o'n daqiqalik va soatlar, to'garaklar, tanlov, olimpiada, matematik kecha.

Аннотация: Закрепление знаний, умений и навыков по организации и проведению внеурочной деятельности по математике в младших классах.

Ключевые слова: внеклассная работа, математические десятиминутки и часы, кружки, конкурс, олимпиада, математический вечер.

Abstract: Strengthening of knowledge, skills and competences in organizing and conducting mathematics extracurricular activities in elementary grades.

Key words: Extracurricular activities, mathematical ten minutes and hours, circles, competition, Olympiad, mathematical night.

The main goal of extracurricular activities in the primary grades is to develop students' interest in science, to collect mathematical facts and information, skills

that complement and deepen the knowledge gained in the basic course of elementary mathematics. "Extracurricular activities" in mathematics are defined as voluntary activities of students based on material related to the program, organized outside the classroom. The following forms of organization of educational work of extracurricular work are distinguished:

1. Independent homework.
2. Individual and group lessons with students.
3. Classes with students capable of mathematics.
4. Extracurricular work in mathematics.
5. Departure to nature with students.

The above forms of work and lesson complement each other. The main question concerns the lesson. The teacher directs all activities in the classroom. In additional exercises, the work is done by the teacher himself or by the students under the guidance of the teacher. Extracurricular activities are aimed at deepening and expanding the mathematical knowledge of students, practicing solving complex examples and problems, familiarizing themselves with some questions that reveal aspects of mathematics that are related to life and not included in the program. You can meet the following types of extracurricular activities: Mathematical ten minutes, interesting mathematical classes, mathematical circles, competitions, interesting mathematical evenings, mathematical excursions. In addition, the creation of a mathematical newspaper, a mathematical quiz and the organization of corners.

As part of extracurricular activities, the following is carried out:

- deepening and expanding knowledge and practical skills;
- development of students' logical thinking, ingenuity, mathematical intelligence;
- to increase interest in mathematics, to identify talented and capable children, to educate exactingness, will, love for work, independence, organization and humanity.

Extracurricular activities have a number of distinctive features in comparison with lessons: 1. According to their content, they do not belong to the mathematics program. But the knowledge to be imparted must correspond to the abilities of the students. 2. Extra-curricular activities should involve all students as much as possible, that is, be interesting. Even underachieving students can become active learners through interest. 3. Extra-curricular activities are organized according to the principle of discreteness, but it is necessary to ensure interest. These exercises are not graded, but students who actively participate in them are encouraged. 4. Depending on the content and forms of training, it can be calculated from 10-12 minutes to 1 hour. 5. Variety of content and forms of extracurricular activities.

In extracurricular activities: interesting word problems, sharp mind problems, funny problems, problems with insufficient or redundant information, logical problems, interesting mathematical events, arithmetic puzzles, games, tricks, puzzles provide historical information and perform other tasks. In school

practice, there are the following forms of extracurricular work: mathematical ten minutes, hourly lessons, mathematical evenings, mathematical circles, matinees, quizzes, competitions, olympiads. The methodology for organizing and conducting extracurricular activities should be based on the following: 1. It is carried out taking into account the knowledge, skills and abilities that students have acquired in the classroom. 2. Extra-curricular activities are organized according to the principles of desire, passion, creativity of students and satisfaction of their individual opinion. 3. The forms of extracurricular work are different from the lessons and have a strong interesting side. A necessary condition for this is the complexity of planning and regularity of work. Types of extracurricular activities:

1. Математические десять минут, часов.
2. Математические кружки.
3. Математические соревнования и олимпиады.
4. Веселые математические вечера и викторины.
5. Математический пресс.
6. Математический экскурс

В заключение можно сказать, что математические вечера могут проходить в формате доклада математического кружка. Цель вечера - учесть знания учащихся по математике, умение применять теорию на практике, навыки устного и письменного счета, пространственное воображение, геометрические понятия и т.д.

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